

The Role Of Fashion In Modern Society

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Abstract: *What is the phenomenon of fashion? Why do millions of people follow trends and dream of becoming a part of the global fashion industry? The influence of fashion on modern youth as well as on people's consciousness. How many garments have changed their functionality in the modern world? What cardinal actions can young people take in pursuit of fashion? The role of fashion in our lives. Choosing your own style.*

Keywords — Style and fashion, trends, fashion industry, self-expression, individuality, the spirit of modern times, artistic and creative contact with fashion.

INTRODUCTION.

Fashion has a huge impact on people's consciousness. The appearance of a person and his ability to present himself beautifully to others is the key to a friendly attitude of people towards his person. The desire to look stylish, popular and confident is the main reason for society's desire to follow the latest fashion trends. For this, a lot of money is spent on the purchase of expensive and modern clothes.

All this is done in order to keep up with fashion and make a favorable impression on other people. It is no secret that our environment, unfortunately, evaluates a new person primarily not by his inner qualities, but by his appearance and clothes.

The role of fashion in our lives. Today, a stylish and glamorous person gives the impression of a successful personality. The fashion world is a kind of big business. Every day, information about the latest fashion innovations is put into a person's mind through various commercials on television, posters on buses, banners, magazines and colorful shop windows. [1]

In the modern world, young people pay special attention to the appearance and style of their peers. It is very difficult to pass by the beautiful storefronts of fashion stores. Most teenagers who cannot afford to buy stylish clothes often become outcasts among their peers. We can safely express the opinion that fashion in the modern world divides society into groups.

Picture-1. Choosing your own style.

Each person is unique by nature. People choose what clothes to wear and what style to follow. The desire to emphasize one's individuality is a decisive factor in choosing clothes. A person's individual physique, age, character, place of work and position also influence the choice of their own style.

The appearance must correspond to a certain situation. Choosing the right clothes will also tell you a lot about your personality. Someone dresses neatly, modestly, but at the same time skillfully emphasizing their natural beauty. The other prefers colorful clothes and bright makeup. It all depends on the individual sense of taste and the ability to combine clothes and things in order to look fashionable, stylish and beautiful. But it is important not to overdo it, so as not to look ridiculous later. [2]

Picture-2. Expression of personality.

The lion's share of all garments were created for the sake of a functional component, and only after popularization became fashionable. Many of them have acquired the status of a symbol of a certain lifestyle, i.e. a means of self-expression. For example, cowboy boots were created as a functional item

for men working in the American West. They were distinguished by the durability and individuality of each model, which was due to the need for durable and perfectly fitting shoes. [3]

Later, the boots got into the wardrobes of people who are far from ranches and cows, but share the basic principles of a “cowboy” attitude to life. The fashion sphere allows people to create an image, express their individuality and arouse interest in their own person. In addition, it is a way to stand out from the crowd and at the same time find like-minded people, feel like part of a certain group who share the same views on style in clothing.

Picture-3. Assessment of a person by his appearance.

Evaluating a person by their appearance is the first step to analyzing a stranger. And this is natural, since at that time it was the only clue for evaluating a person whom I saw for the first time in my life. The chosen clothes reflect the taste of this person and his social status.

People often donate a huge amount of money for beauty and good clothes in order to forget their worries and problems at least for a while. By shopping, they cheer themselves up. Fashionable and beautiful clothes can also reflect a person's state of mind. Fashion is an integral part of society. Following fashion, dressing stylishly, beautifully and expensively is not a crime, but simply a desire to be like everyone else or even better. [2]

The spirit of the times. While fashion trends look random and unpredictable, styles often evolve in accordance with large-scale cultural movements. As the legendary Coco Chanel said: “Fashion lives not only in dresses. Fashion is in the sky, on the streets, fashion is connected with ideas, our lifestyle and everything that happens around us”.

She is able to talk about what people wore during a certain period of time, which, in turn, gives an extensive understanding of their lifestyle. Consider the hippie culture prevalent in the 1970 s. Flowers, bell-bottoms, flowing dresses and the “Peace” sign had no functional meaning, these garments expressed the values of an entire generation. Namely,

love, peace, cooperation, alternative and new types of thinking. Ticks and flowing dresses represented a departure from the old society with a strict dress code and norms of behavior. The hippie style helped people to declare their values and break away from the aesthetics of the past. [1]

Artistic and creative energy. Everyone knows that painting, prose, photography are used as forms of artistic expression, fashion is no exception. Creating clothing models and wardrobe selection helps to release creative energy. At the beginning of the 20th century, art and design were closely linked, for example, in those days couturiers collected paintings and were friends with artists. Today, art and fashion have moved a little apart from each other, but the creation of clothing collections will always remain a part of artistic expression.

A sense of change. What is more interesting about fashion? Many people just love to follow the latest trends in the fashion industry, this is their hobby, one might say, a hobby. Just imagine, designers, stylists, photographers and models are doing a tremendous job to capture new collections for lookbooks, magazines and online publications. [3]

Every season brings something unexpected, fashion connoisseurs are looking forward to new outfits from leading and emerging brands. So why do people need fashion? So that they can believe in the ability to change in every sense of the word, to evolve, because humanity always strives to move forward and improve. As the French philosopher Gilles Lipovetsky said: “Fashion is one of the manifestations of modern ingenuity, a person's desire to make himself the master of the situation, the conditions in which he lives”.

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